

ETIQUETTE OF COMMUNICATION IN TERTIARY INSTITUTIONS
ADMINISTRATION FILE MINUTING TO ELIMINATE FRAUD

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Abstract

Etiquette of administrative communication, especially, file minuting is one of the essential qualities of Colleges of Education administration that promotes acceptable rules of communication through file. It regulates unethical file minuting. Intentional wrongful file minuting is synonymous with administrative fraud just like financial fraud in financial parlance. People least expect that fraud cuts across various disciplines other than finance. Administration is the life wire of any organization as it houses both human and material resources. Administrative communication is also a specialized communication where administrative fraud can be committed. This research intends to look at etiquette of administrative communication to eliminate fraud using Deontology Theory and Deductive Thematic Analysis of Secondary expository research method. The review revealed that administrative fraud mostly take place within the clerical, executive and even officers levels where tampering with the pagination and minuting of offline files can completely distort records of information in the file. This paper recommends that Registrars who are the administrative heads of tertiary institutions and responsible for record keeping should be more vigilant with submissions in the offline files to curb administrative fraud menace through intentional tampering with pagination or defacing original write-ups through minuting for personal gain.

Key Words: *Etiquette, Administrative communication, Fraud, Administrative fraud and Tertiary institution.*

Introduction

Every profession promulgates to her members etiquettes to guide its operation. This is to make a seamless operation for members to achieve the desired goals of the profession. The etiquette of communication in the file minuting can control administrative fraud. Fraud is a worldwide phenomenon that is hunting mostly the financial, administrative, educational and political development the world over. This is because fraud is like a canker worm that retards progress. Fraud is one of the foundations of corruption and injustice in the society. Administration on the other hand is the life wire of any organization as it manages and sees to the suitable development and growth of both human and material resources.

However, many administrators are not conversant with the concept of administrative fraud and corruption. Every day administrators minute submissions inside files and equally minute on files to indicate the next person to treat the file, the page to be treated, the comment to respond to and the date it was treated by the last administrator or technical person. Little or not do these administrators know that the minuting inside the file can be fraudulently removed and the minute on the back of the file can serve as witness for what is supposed to be inside it.

However, paucity of empirical research works in the field of file minuting in administrative communication makes this study to adopt deductive thematic narration of secondary sources using conceptual review.

Conceptual Background

Public and Business Administration studies do focus on high level administrative theories to achieve organizational goals while the day to day file minuting communication is not attended to.

More often than not when holders of diplomas and degrees in administration are employed, they have to go through orientation from the hands of experienced Clerical staff to be able to communicate through files which is the means through which communication takes place within an organization. This leaves file communication knowledge restricted to only on-the-job training.

However, since CORECOEN wants to professionalize administrative studies by breaking it down for the understanding of any person wishing to join this profession, it becomes imperative on the Conference to professionalize administration in tertiary institutions, more especially within the Colleges of Education sub sector.

Therefore, coming up with “dos” and “donts” in file minuting communication as one of the professional administrative communication becomes necessary for the understanding of both our professional members and others interested in this field of communication. Paucity of

empirical research works in this field for review has resulted to deductive thematic narration of secondary sources using conceptual review. The need for this aspect of file minuting communication for the benefits of professional in this field and other related ones informed the reason for this work.

The purpose of this study is therefore, to use conceptual secondary sources to analyse the “dos” and “don’ts” in file minuting to avoid administrative file minuting communication fraud.

Basically, some conceptual clarifications are presented below:

Etiquette: This refers to in this context as set of rules of acceptable administrative communication through file minuting in Colleges of Education in Nigeria.

Communication: This refers in this context to communication in the organization like Colleges of Education in Nigeria.

Fraud: Fraud in this work refers to intentional wrongful or criminal deception and manipulations that can lead to financial or administrative personal gain in Colleges of Education in Nigeria.

Administrative fraud: This refers to in this context as intentional wrongful or criminal deceptive manipulative file minuting communication that can lead to administrative or personal gain in the Colleges of Education sub sector in Nigeria.

Tertiary institution: refers to in this context as the Colleges of Education sub sector in Nigeria.

Methodology

This research work used secondary expository research method or literature review to review related conceptual literature on etiquette of administrative communication through file minuting. According to Snyder (2019), literature review is more or less systematic way of collecting and synthesizing previous research. This is because a well conducted review as a research method creates a firm foundation for advancing knowledge and facilitating theory development. It is an excellent way of synthesizing research findings to show evidence on a

meta-level and to uncover areas in which more research is needed, which is a critical component of creating a theoretical frameworks and building conceptual models.

Theoretical Framework

This work used the Deontology Theory which Immanuel Kant, a German Philosopher of the 18th century derived from the Greek word “deon” meaning “duty” and “logos” meaning “science”. He believed that ethical actions follow universal moral laws, such as “Don’t lie”, “Don’t steal”, “Don’t cheat”, etc. Deontology is an ethical theory that uses rules to distinguish “right” from “wrong”. This implies that this theory requires that people follow the rules and do their duty rightly.

This theory also relates to the “dos” and “don’ts” in administrative file minuting communication. This can be referred to as “etiquette of administrative file minuting communication” so as to regulate administrative fraud for a better communication. In communication, deontological reasoning entails that there is need for desirable character traits to be identified through the use of concepts such as: dignity, respect, good intention and dutiful in communicating just like ethical codes of journalists, public relations, advertising, etc. This explains the reason for the use of this theory as the theoretical framework for this paper.

Conceptual Review

Etiquette of Communication in Tertiary Institutions Administration File Minuting

Literature review can be narrative or integrative, systematic, semi-systematic and meta-analysis. Secondary expository research requires research and investigation of an idea, gather supporting evidence, and present a point of view or argument on a topic. This work used semi-systematic review using themes in qualitative research by identifying, analyzing and reporting patterns in the form of themes.

The Registry

Yakusak (2021), observes that Registry is a place where official records are kept or a book or system for keeping an official record of items. He classified registry into two, (1) Open Registry and (2) Secret Registry.

1. Open Registry

Open Registry is accessible to Registry staff. It stores open policy and personal files containing documents that are open to many people.

2. Secret Registry

Secret Registry is accessible to only dedicated officer(s). It is the storage of records and retrieval of confidential files containing personal credentials.

Registry, according to Kailes and Enders (2014), is a place where official records are kept, or a book or system for keeping an official record of items. Registry data items can be things, e.g motor vehicles, personnel, etc.

Functions of a Registry

Yakusak (2021), identified functions of a registry as follows:

The registry is mainly in charge of (I) storage of files (personal, open, secret (policy) and confidential) (ii) storing, retrieving and tracking of files (III) management of records (IV) documentation of records (V) receiving and filing of mails and general administration.

Importance of Registry

1. Keeps and preserves organisational records. Registry is the engine room that keeps records of the organization for retrieval when required. It could be intra or inter organizational records. These records include credentials of staff, employment records, employee communication with the employer amongst others.

2. Ensures organisational efficiency. Organisation needs records to be efficient in its operation. The registry preserves the needed records for the organization to be effective and efficient.
3. It is the life wire of every organization. The life of an organization depends on needed records and the registry keeps, manages and administer these records.

Benefits of Registry

Efficiency. Records are better organised and easily located for retrieval

Good decision making. Access to records and precedent leads to good decision making.

Good image. The registry preserves records of the organization and makes it easy for the organization to access its records. This improves the image of organization to the outside world.

Continuity. Organisation can retrieve records of its past operation from the registry which enhances continuity in the system. Even when staff leave the organization, their performance in the organization can be traced through their records in the registry.

Preservation. It enhances Institutional memory and therefore facilitates sustainable growth and development.

File as Channel of Organisational Communication

File jacket is the first thing to understand before delving into its contents. It is a flat folder that are closed on three sides and in a unique form used to keep documents secured, yet easily accessible. It is used to hold many pages of documents.

A file jacket has the name of the organization on top of the front page. It has four identical columns placed in four places, 1. under the name head 2. Right side 3. Left side and 4. Bottom side. These are made up two columns each containing file number and volume. The front side also contain nine columns made up of three sets of addresses such as “To” meaning addressed

to,”Page” showing the page to find the communication and “Date” showing the date the communication was made.

In writing the file number, you start with abbreviation of the organization e.g. Federal College of Education to be abbreviated as “FCE”. Then Technical, to be shortened as “T”. Then the location of the organization, e.g. Bichi, to be represented by “B”. Then the department e.g. Registry Establishment, to be represented by “EST”. Then comes the volume, e.g. Vol. I. Then the page, e.g. 1, to show page 1. (FCET/B//EST/Vol.1/1).The other three sides of the folder should contain the same information.

File Jacket Contents

File contents to Gambo and Manu (2021), means a collection of papers on a specific subject matter, which is recognized from a specific serial number, or a file number, and has many correspondence notes, and an appendix to correspondence.

They classified file types based on the purpose they are created to serve as follows:

- i. Lost file: This is the type of file whereby in the day-to-day running of office activities, circumstances occur that the where about of a certain file is not found, vigorous efforts should be made to locate the where about of such a file. If after thorough search the file could not be located, such a file is declared “lost”.
- ii. Temporary file: A temporary file is opened when the main file is either misplaced, missing or cannot be realized owing to proceeding actions on it.
- iii. Pending file: When a file is with an officer awaiting appropriate action, such a file is considered pending.
- iv. Subject file: This type of file is otherwise known as sub-file. These are files opened when the subject matters although closely related are divergent from the subject dealt with in the main file.

- v. Case file: A case file is opened in an organization when there is a special matter to be treated, for the time being i.e. temporary.

Other Classification of Files in the Registry

- i. Gambo and Manu (2021), also classified files to either be personal file, policy file, secret file, confidential file or temporary file.
- ii. Personal file: This could be sub divided into two: 1. Individual open personal file 2. Individual confidential file.
- iii. Individual open file. These are files of individuals that carry personal documents that are not confidential in nature. They are brown or khaki in colour
- iv. Confidential file: These are individual files that carry individual documents that are confidential in nature or are not supposed to be exposed to unauthorized persons. These files used for storage of credentials of individuals.
- v. Secret file: This refers to secret policy files that not supposed to be exposed to unauthorized persons. They are usually red in colour
- vi. Policy file: Policy file refers to subjects files. They are not for individual staff but subjects to house correspondences that are not on individual staff
- vii. Temporary file (T-File): These are files opened to enable correspondences to be treated when the original file is in movement or when it is not seen and the correspondence cannot be delayed. This file is labeled in pencil and not in ink. But when the original file is recovered, the contents of the temporary file is emptied back into the original file.

Filing

Having discussed the concept of registry and file, it is good to delve into filing which is the transmission of administrative communication.

Filing to Gambo and Manu (2021), is a systematic arrangement of keeping administrative correspondence and records which enable quick reference whenever needed in the future. It is the placing of documents and papers in acceptable containers according to some predetermined arrangements so that any time required, it can be located with ease.

According to them, a good filing system should have the following requirements:

- i. The system should be kept simple to reduce errors and to facilitate all employees' use of the system;
- ii. Files should contain information which is linked to the activities and functions which they document;
- iii. The system should have a structured numeric or alphanumeric referencing system in which each element corresponds with a function of the file title to a maximum of four elements. Types of file referencing systems include: alphabetical; numerical; alphanumeric; and keyword.

Kailes and Enders (2014), classified filing into five methods as follows:

1. Filing by subject/category. It is a system where files and folders of documents are arranged in accordance with their subjects. It therefore uses alphabetical order of the subjects;
2. Filing in alphabetical order. It is a system where files and folders of documents are arranged in order of alphabets of the names of the persons or institutions concern with such files. This method is easy to understand, time saving, very efficient for retrieval and does not require separate index;
3. Filing by numbers/numerical order. This type is a system of organizing records through the use of numbers that appear on the materials. It deals with classifying of files using numbers as headings. Numerical filing is a method in which files and folders are arranged in order of number. All files and folders are classified and given separate number. In this type of filing alphabetical index is required. It includes name, address, phone number, subject and other information along with number. This can be used for large organization;

4. Filing by places/geographical order. It is a system where files and folders of documents are arranged in accordance to the geographical location of firms, organization or persons. Under this, the name of places are written in the files and arranged in alphabetical order or numbers. It is used in multi- national companies with branches located in various countries, states or locations;
5. Filing by dates/chronological order. This is the filing system where files and folders of documents are arranged in order of their date, day, and time. This sequence could be according to the date the documents were received, or date and time the files were created. In this case, the most recent date is in front of or on top of the previous ones. This can only be suitable for specific things, like receipts. It is suitable for small organization.

It is expensive for smaller organization

Items Required to Open a File

Gambo and Manu (2021), listed the following as items required to open a file:

File jacket, file tag, punch, ruler, eraser, sharpener, stencil as well as pencil/ biro (red, black/blue).

Procedure for Opening a File

File number to be written in the index register. Index register contains records of serial number of files.

Professional File Communication Symbols: Coding and Decoding for Easy Understanding

As stated earlier in this paper, professional administrators use professional file communication symbols and abbreviations that can only be understood by administrative professionals, except un-coded for them. Below are few of them:

Symbols

X - Urgent

XX - Today

XXX – Now or immediately

Key File Minuting Abbreviations

P.A – Put away

BU – Bring up

FYI – For your information

FYNA – For your necessary action

FYINA – For your information and necessary action

FYC – For your consideration

F&R – File and return

ASAP – As soon as possible

A.B.C – At back cover

A.F.C – At front cover

AYC – At your convenience

AOB – Any other business

Ag. Acting

AT – Action taken

NFAN – No further action needed

N/A – Not applicable

H/W – Here with

IAW – In accordance with

I/C – In charge of

IDC – In due course

IVO – In view of

IFO – In favour of

IRO – In respect of

C.C – Carbon copy

BUF – Back up file (to bring up close volume of the file)

B/F – Brpught forward

C/F – Carry forward

C/O – Care of

SPK/SWF - Speak with file

UFS - Under flying seal (to pass through a higher Authority)

Dept. – Department

Enc. - Enclosure F & PA – File and put away

F.N.A - For necessary action

F.F.A – For further action

K.IV - Keep in view

WIP – Work in progress

O.K – All Correct

Pp – Pages

P - Page

Para. – Paragraph

Prov – Provost

DP – Deputy Provost

Reg. Registrar

Burs – Bursar

CL – College Librarian

DOWS – Director of Works and Services

DR – Deputy Registrar

DB – Deputy Bursar

ADR – Assistant Deputy Registrar

ADB – Assistant Deputy Bursar

CSO – Chief Security Officer

IGR – Internal generated revenue

QA –Quality Assurance.

Ref. – Reference

SFC – Submitted for your consideration

SFS – Submitted for signature

S.RV - Store Receipt Voucher

Attributes of a Registry Staff

Good appearance: Registry staff are the gateway for people wishing to communicate to higher authorities of an organization. They should therefore appear neatly to give a good image of the organization.

Dedicated: Registry staff have to be present at their duty post because people can approach them at any official working time.

Loyalty to the organisation: Registry staff must be loyal to the authorities of the organization.

Hardworking: Registry staff have to be loyal to the authorities of the organization for them to be trusted.

Courteous but firm: Registry staff have to be simple to be approached by people but to be firm in upholding the ethical values of their profession.

Confidentiality: Registry staff have to know their job very well so that they can be confident in doing their job. They should hear more, see more but talk less by concentrating on their job.

Accessible: Registry staff have to be accessible during official working hours.

Honesty/integrity: Registry staff have to be honest so as to be trusted by their organization authorities.

Unauthorised disclosure of official information or Information leakage: Registry staff are not supposed to divulge information under their trust to unauthorized persons.

Registry staff have to balance the minutes on documents pages inside the communication file with the minutes at the front cover page of the file. This is because any variant in the two can lead to administrative file minuting communication fraud.

The Filing Clerical Officer Identified Unethical and Fraudulent Activities

The following issues can constitute fraudulent activities in filing administration:

1. Any difference between the letter numbering inside page of file and the front cover letter numbering is an indication of a fraudulent unauthorized removal of a page or pages. The page numbering inside the file must correspond with the letter numbering on the front cover of the file.
2. Unauthorized removal of any page from a file

This entails an Officer removing any page from an official file unless authorized to do so. Such removal are mostly done based on wrong intents.

3. Unauthorized exchange of paged document in a file

Pages of documents in the file need not to be exchanged except with proper authorization to avoid wrong interpretations.

4. Unauthorized alteration on a document in a file or Falsification of records.

Documents in a file are not supposed to be unnecessarily altered without permission to do so. This is because sensitive documents that affect some people can be altered thereby presenting wrong information to it decoders.

5. Unauthorized cancellation on a document in a file

Cancellation on official documents in a file without written approval is not acceptable in administrative etiquette. This is seen as a criminal act.

6. Using eraser to change any writing in the file

It is only acceptable practice is to neatly cross a mistake committed inside an official file using ruler. Then you can write the correct one so that the reader can clearly see what was earlier written wrongly to avoid doubts.

7. Using correction fluid on any document in the file or suppression of records

Just like it is illegal to erase wordings on official document in a file, the use of correction fluid to change either a word or otherwise also suppresses the record.

8. Refusal to sign a minute in a file.

It is unethical for an officer to refuse to sign after minuting (officially commenting on an issue) in a file.

9. Refusal to indicate one's rank on a minute of a file

It is equally unethical for an officer to refuse to indicate his/her rank after officially commenting on an issue.

10. Defacing any written material in the file

All documents in official files are official, hence, should not be defaced.

11. Hiding files for personal reasons

Hiding an official file is unethical. File handlers should avoid doing that.

12. Refusing to act on a file as directed to one's desk

It is not only unethical, but tantamount to refuse to act on an official file designated for one's action.

13. Undue delay to act on file as directed to one's desk or withholding of files

A transparent officer does not delay an official file unnecessarily. As an official file reach one's table, it is advisable for such an officer to act on it immediately.

14. Refusal to file a document due to a file

Just like it is unethical to refuse to act on an official file on one's table, it is equally unethical for an officer to refuse to file any official document in its appropriate file.

Don'ts in File Minuting

In file minuting, it is ethical for one to avoid the following acts referred to as "don'ts":

1. When minuting at the top of a document where there is no any typed or hand written text, the initiating officer should not letter number the minutes.
2. The communicating officer should not begin a page with letter numbering.
3. Never continue letter numbering from another page to another.
4. Never number paragraphs with alphabets (a, b, c, etc)
5. Never number the first paragraph.
6. Never number the second paragraph with one (1), but with 2 (as it is assumed that the first unnumbered paragraph has a silent number 1).
7. Never differentiate the letter numbering of outside cover page and those of the inside page.

8. Never leave what was addressed to you on the front cover uncrossed before you address to the next recipient. If you did not cross it, this means that you are yet to treat what was addressed to you.
9. Never minute on the back of a page that there is an attachment.
10. Never minute before the signature, name and address of a writer of a communicator.
11. Never deface a write up with minuting.
12. Don't addressing the recipient with his name or qualification.
13. The officer communicating should not end his minute without not writing his rank.
(This is because this does not indicate ownership of the communication).
14. The officer communicating should not end his minutes without not endorsing the communication.
15. Never refuse to act on a file as directed to your desk is not only unethical, but an insubordination act to refuse to act on an official file designated for one's action.
16. Never allow an undue delay to act on file as directed to your desk or withholding of files.
17. Avoid any difference between the letter numbering inside page of file and the front cover letter numbering as this is an indication of a fraudulent unauthorized removal of a page or pages.

Differences Between Irregularities and Errors

Irregularities could arise due to human recurrent or systemic error of not correctly following the regulations. Error on the other hand is an irregularity that is one-off or just done once and if discovered is quickly corrected. A systemic irregularity is a recurrent error due to serious failings in management and control systems designed to ensure correct compliance with rules and regulations.

Differences Between Financial Fraud and Administrative Fraud

Financial fraud broadly refer to an intentional act of deception involving financial transactions for purpose of personal gain. It involves misappropriation of funds. Fraud is a crime, and it can also be a civil law violation. Administrative fraud refers to intended act of wrongful or criminal deception involving administrative file communication for personal gain. It is an intentional unethical administrative act for personal gain. Simply put, administrative fraud refers to fraudulent activities committed within an organization or by individuals who work in position of trust within an organization like registry staff, through manipulation of records. While financial fraud involves misappropriation of funds, administrative fraud involves manipulation of records.

Differences Between Administrative Fraud and Administrative Irregularities

While an administrative fraud refers to an intentional unethical administrative act for personal gain, or intentional wrongful or criminal deception involving administrative file communication for personal gain (having criminal intent). Administrative fraud involves manipulation of records. An administrative irregularity arises due to human recurrent or systemic error of not correctly following the regulations but without criminal intent.

Differences Between Administrative Irregularities and Administrative Errors

Administrative irregularity could arise due to human recurrent or systemic administrative error of not correctly following the regulations while an administrative error on the other hand is an administrative irregularity that is one-off or just done once and if discovered is quickly corrected. An administrative irregularity could be one-off or systemic. A one-off administrative irregularity is that irregularity that is recurrent or systemic.

Deductive Thematic Narrative Analysis of Expository Review

The Etiquette of an Office Filing Officer

A Cleical staff in charge of filing and retrieving documents under the analogue system works under an etiquette of ‘dos’ and ‘don’ts’.

If the Clerical Officer commits the 'don'ts', this study deduce as follows:

This means that the Clerical Officer or any officer minuting at the top of a document where there is no any typed or hand written text, the initiating officer should not letter number the minutes. It is also unethical for the communicating officer to begin a page with letter numbering. He should neither continue letter numbering from another page to another nor number paragraphs with alphabets (a, b, c, etc). Equally, never number the first paragraph and start numbering the second paragraph with 2 instead of 1 (as it is assumed that the first unnumbered paragraph has a silent number 1).

Since the difference between the letter numbering inside page of file and the front cover letter numbering is an indication of a fraudulent unauthorized removal of a page or pages, therefore, make sure that the page numbering inside the file must correspond with the letter numbering on the front cover of the file. This means that any variance between the two numbering is a fraud.

The officer minuting is not supposed to leave what was addressed to him on the front cover uncrossed before he address to the next recipient. If he did not cross it, this means that he is yet to treat what was addressed to him. The minuting officer is not supposed to minute on the back of a page that there is an attachment following the writeup. He is not also supposed to minute before the signature, name and address of a writer of a communicator, but should leave space before minuting so as not to deface the writeup. He is not supposed to addressing the recipient with the recipient name or qualification as this is unethical. The recipient should be addressed by position or rank.

The Clerical Officer or any officer performing this duty cannot intentionally remove any page from a file without authority. Removing a page or pages without authority can lead to manipulation and distortion of information which may eventually amount to fraud.

If an officer exchange pages of document in a file without authority, this act can distort the flow and arrangement of document which could amount to fraud.

Unauthorized alteration on a document in a file by any officer can change the original meaning of the information which can be translated to fraud.

Any cancellation in a document in the file without being authorized can hide and suppress the original meaning and become suspicious that something unethical was intended by the officer that did such cancellation.

Using eraser to change any writing in the file will hide and suppress the original error that was corrected and can be suspicious to the reader.

Just like using eraser to cancel documents, using correction fluid on any writing in the file also hides the original error that was corrected and can be suspicious to the reader.

If an officer refuses to sign a minute in a file, it can be interpreted that the officer will not want to own up to the write up.

Refusing to indicate one's rank on a minute of a file is an indication that the officer wants to hide his identity of the minuting.

Defacing any document in a file by minuting within the writeup affect the presentation of such documents in a Court of law as an exhibit.

Hiding files for personal reasons delays or denies the presentation of such files at the appropriate time, hence, justice is denied.

Refusing to act on a file as directed to one's desk is an outright denial of the writer's right.

Undue delay to act on file as directed to one's desk means delay of presentation of such files at the appropriate time, hence, justice is denied.

Refusal to file a document due to a file means that the communication that is not filed is denied treatment. This is going to affect the organization negatively and retard its healthy progress and smooth running.

Little or not do these administrators know that the minutes inside the file can be fraudulently removed and the minute on the back of the file can serve as witness for what is supposed to be inside the file. Therefore, balancing the minutes on documents pages inside the communication file with the minutes at the front cover page of the file. This is because any variant in the two can lead to administrative file minuting communication fraud.

Conclusion

The etiquette of file minuting administrative communication deals with “dos” and “don’ts” of file communication. Administrative fraud involves manipulation of records. In file minuting communication, administrative fraud refers to manipulation of file minuting records by registry staff entrusted with these records.

Equally, balancing the minutes on documents pages inside the communication file with the minutes at the front cover page of the file is one way to curbing administrative fraud. This is because any variant in the two can lead to administrative file minuting communication fraud. Therefore, fraud does not only apply to financial matters alone as administrative communication fraud is the window to financial fraud. This is because administrative fraud in an organisation, if unchecked, can later lead to financial fraud which can further lead to the total collapse of the organization.

Policy Recommendations

1. Conference of Registrars of Colleges of Education in Nigeria (CORECOEN) should continue to use ANCOEPA to train administrators on etiquette of administrative professionals file minuting communication rudiments. The training should breaking down the process for easy understanding.
2. Management of Colleges of Education in Nigeria at all levels should be attentive in controlling administrative fraud to curb its spread to financial.

3. Registrars of Colleges of Education in Nigeria should assign some senior officers to monitor file minuting communication so that administrative fraud is prevented at the initiation stage.
4. The management of tertiary institutions should, henceforth, pay greater attention to both manual and automated filing system to prevent administrative communication fraud so as to save the integrity and mitigate the collapse of tertiary institutions in Nigeria.
5. Registry staff should always endeavor to balance the minutes on documents pages inside the communication file with the minutes at the front cover page of the file to avoid administrative file minuting communication fraud.

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